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The Future is Virtual: Exploring the Impact of VR on Science Education

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Technological advancements more specifically virtual reality (VR) technologies are causing a lot of alteration in many aspects of life such as in the world of entertainment, healthcare, business, engineering, and even in the field of education. Undoubtedly, VR can revolutionize the way teachers teach and the way students learn.

The current applications of VR in education include virtual field trips, remote learning, practical training, medical training, teaching students with special needs, teaching anatomy and dissection, game-based learning, virtual reality labs, collaborative learning, and aiding learning new language (10 Contemporary Use Cases of Virtual Reality in Education, 2021). These VR apps are being used in different areas of knowledge such as Arts, History, Natural Sciences, and other disciplines.

Considering the nature of science, there are many complex processes and abstract ideas that the unaided teacher finds difficult to put the ideas across to the students. Teaching science requires the use of multisensory learning but due to many factors, there are some limitations to what the teacher can provide inside the classroom. Because of these limitations, the potential of VR to provide a "life-like" experience is very promising.

Nowadays, there are many VR apps available that can be used for science education (Galadzhii, 2023). There is the Anatomy VR, the 4D Anatomy VR, and the A Journey into the Brain in VR which can be used in teaching human anatomy and the InMind VR2 can be used to teach the different hormones. The National Geographic Explore VR and the Ocean Rift can be used as an aid in teaching concepts of Ecology and Biogeography. For Earth science, there is the Titans of Space VR and the Apollo 11 VR which are about outer space and heavenly bodies.

Moreover, Discovery VR is a multidisciplinary app with content applicable to natural sciences along with YouTube VR. The Safari Tours Adventures VR 4D can be utilized by the science teacher to provide students with unique and exciting experiences that allow them to study animals in their natural habitat. The Cleanopolis VR can be used to teach about environmental protection, climate change, and sustainability concepts. (Johnes, 2023)

Many benefits that can be derived from using VR in teaching (Pros and Cons of Using Virtual Reality in Education | LITSLINK Blog, 2019). It provides a near-life experience

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to students that most educators struggle to provide like exploring different places impossible to reach such as the bottom of the ocean, the peak of a mountain, and outer space by making it seem real. It generally improves the quality of students' experience which leads to an in-depth understanding of the concepts and greater retention because of its multisensory appeal. The use of VR also contributes positively to establishing student engagement primarily because students nowadays prefer gadgets and digital experiences and because VR incorporates the gaming reward system increasing students' motivation.

On the Other hand, VR undermines human interaction leading to a failure to develop interpersonal skills among the students and can also lead to some sort of addiction. VR also lacks flexibility and students cannot just ask questions unlike in the conventional classroom where the students can interact directly with the live teacher. There might be some free VR apps available, but the gadgets needed are quite expensive and require funding that not all schools can afford, causing inequalities rather than erasing them.

The impact of VR in education is multifaceted and complex. Although it has the potential to improve certain aspects of students' engagement and mastery of the content, they also come with risks and challenges that need to be managed carefully. As educational technologists strive to discover the potential of VR in other aspects of education and become integrated into the educational system, it is important to strike a balance between the benefits and risks of these technologies to ensure a positive impact primarily among the students.

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